

SOP for Colour Measurement in Fresh and Boiled Plantain using a Chromameter

Dschang, Cameroon, January 2025

Gérard NGOH NEWILAH, University of Dschang, Dschang, Cameroon

Socrate GOUMMELI, University of Dschang, Dschang, Cameroon

Dallonnes FANGUENG KAMGO, University of Yaounde I, Cameroon

Cédric KENDINE VEPOWO, University of Douala, Douala, Cameroon

This report has been written in the framework of the RTB Breeding project, Quality-component (under CIRAD coordination), as a continuation of work initiated under the RTBfoods project.

To be cited as:

Grard NGOH NEWILAH, Socrate GOUMMELI, Dallannes FANGUENG KAMGO, Cdric KENDINE VEPOWO (2025). *SOP for Colour Measurement in Fresh and Boiled Plantain using a Chromameter*. Dschang, Cameroon: RTB Breeding, Standard Operating Protocol, 11 p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15116129>

Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the RTB Breeding project, through a sub-grant from the International Potato Center (CIP) to the French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD), Montpellier, France, incorporated in the grant agreement INV-041105 between CIP and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF).

Image cover page  CIRAD.

RTBfoods / RTB Breeding

SOP: Colour Measurement in Fresh and Boiled Plantain using a Chromameter

Date: 10/01/2025

Release: 1

Written by: Gérard NGOH NEWILAH

For information on this SOP please contact:

- Gérard NGOH NEWILAH (gbngoh@gmail.com)
- Socrate GOUMMELI (goummeli6socrates@gmail.com)
- Dallannes FANGUENG KAMGO (rdibango@gmail.com)
- Cédric KENDINE VEPOWO (kendinec@gmail.com)

This document has been reviewed by:

Final validation by:

Eglantine FAUVELLE (CIRAD)

31/03/2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of Figures	4
List of tables.....	4
1 SCOPE AND APPLICATION.....	6
2 REFERENCES.....	6
3 PRINCIPLE.....	6
4 REAGENTS	7
5 APPARATUS.....	7
6 PROCEDURE	8
7 EXPRESSION OF RESULTS.....	10
8 CRITICAL POINTS OR NOTE ON THE PROCEDURE.....	10

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1 : CIELAB colour space (Hunt, 1991)	7
Figure 2 : Workflow of colour measurements using a Chromameter.....	9

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 : List of apparatus and their uses.....	7
Table 2 : Sample data recording for colour of fruits	10

ABSTRACT

Plantain pulp and peel colour are very important in the final decision of a consumer as regards adoption of different varieties. This is done by human judging using the sense of sight but remains subjective since different people may perceive differently. This then brings in the importance of an instrumental technique to render colour determination more objective. The chromameter is an advanced instrument used for quantifying and analysing colours by capturing light reflected from a surface and converting it into numerical values that represent colour attributes. The chromameter employs standardised colour spaces (CIE L*, a* and b*) to facilitate consistent communication across the different measured fruits (raw and boiled fruits). The use of chromameter enhances precision in colour matching and quality assessment that facilitate comparison between different ripening stages of plantain, revealing colour variations due to cooking which greatly impacts consumer perception.

Keywords: Colour, Chromameter, Consumer, Quality Assessment

1 SCOPE AND APPLICATION

Agronomic yield and technological performance are considered important criteria by plantain producers and processors, but the main criterion for consumers is the sensory quality (colour, taste, texture) (Ngho Newilah et al., 2021). Colour is one of the important sensory properties that determine the acceptability of food products (Abiodun et al., 2017). Consumers rely primarily on pulp colour to judge the quality of boiled plantain. The colour of both peel and pulp are therefore important selection criteria since consumers make specific correlations between the colour and the overall quality of raw and boiled plantain products. Consumers associate peel colour with a specific flavour or use (Dadzie & Orchard, 1997). Although the current demand for plantains and their products is high, consumer needs and tastes are changing over time (Horvat et al., 2019). The use of colour charts to determine the colour of foods is subjective and may be biased by many errors. Several objective and reliable instrumental methods have been established to determine the colour of plantains using a chromameter through the CIE L*, a* and b* tristimulus parameters.

2 REFERENCES

Ngho Newilah G., Kendine C., Takam A., Bouniol, A., Rolland-Sabaté, A., Meli Meli, V., Yong Lemoumoum, J. S., Forsythe, L., Dufour, D., & Fliedel, G. (2021). Analysis of consumer-oriented quality characteristics of raw and boiled plantains in Cameroon: Implication for breeding. *International Journal of Food Science & Technology*, 56(3), 1135–1147. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijfs.14812>

Abiodun A., Akinoso R. & Dauda O. (2017). Evaluation of colour in white and yellow trifoliate yam flours in relation to harvesting periods and pre-processing methods. *Agrosearch*, 17(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.4314/agrosh.v17i1.1>

Dadzie, K., & Orchard, J. (1997). Évaluation post-récolte des hybrides de bananiers et bananiers plantains: critères et méthodes. INIBAP. http://www.biodiversityinternational.org/fileadmin/_migrated/uploads/tx_news/Routine_postharvest_screening_of_banana_plantain_hybrids__Criteria_and_methods_235_FR.pdf

Horvat, A., Granato, G., Fogliano, V., & Luning, P. A. (2019). Understanding consumer data use in new product development and the product life cycle in European food firms – An empirical study. *Food Quality and Preference*, 76, 20–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2019.03.008>

Hunt, R.W.G. (1991). *Measuring Colour*, 2nd Ed., pp. 75–76, Ellis Horwood, New York, NY

3 PRINCIPLE

The CIE L*, a* and b* tristimulus parameters were determined in triplicate using a chromameter (CR-410, Konica Minolta Sensing Inc. Osaka, Japan). The chromameter operates according to the CIE L*, a* and b* colour schemes with L* representing brightness (ranging from 0 = black and 100 = white); a* representing red-green (positive values are red, negative values are green and 0 is neutral), and b* representing yellow-blue (positive values are yellow, negative values are blue and 0 is neutral) (Hunt, 1991). However, the Hunter Lab L*, a*, b* values are directly read using portable Minolta CR-400 Chroma Meter. L* is an approximate measurement of luminosity, which is the property according to which each colour can be considered as equivalent to a member of the greyscale, between black and white (Fig 1).

Figure 1: CIELAB colour space (Hunt, 1991)

4 REAGENTS

No reagent is required

5 APPARATUS

Table 1 : List of apparatus and their uses

Material	Image
<p>Stainless steel knife.</p> <p>The stainless-steel knife is carbon steel with added chromium to resist corrosion and other elements which increase performance levels.</p>	
<p>Stainless spoon</p> <p>Cooking spoon with rubber handle (insulator) used during plantain boiling</p>	
<p>Sample trays</p> <p>Disposable antistatic square weighing trays.</p>	

Material	Image
<p>Cooking pots</p> <p>The pot is stainless with an advantage of heating up rapidly during cooking</p>	
<p>Chroma meter</p> <p>(Minolta CR- 400 Chroma Meter)</p>	

6 PROCEDURE

The colour of plantain fruit samples (raw pulps, boiled pulps and fruit peels) were determined using a CR-400/410 Chromameter (Konica Minolta Japan) that functions on the bases of the Hunter scale (L^* , a^* , b^*) system. The chromameter is calibrated against a white standard (provided with the equipment) at the beginning of each measurement.

The plantain bunch was harvested at physiological maturity stage (i.e appearance of a ripe fruit either on the first hand, or the second hand of the bunch) early in the morning. The bunch was carried to the laboratory. The fruits from the second and third hands were removed and washed with running water. With respect to the sample, procedures were as follows (Fig2)

- Peel colour was measured by placing the measuring head on the fruit surface (peel surface) and taking approximately 2-3 readings (at the middle, at the apex and the peduncle of each fruit). The mean value was considered as the peel colour.
- Raw pulp colour on the other hand was measured by cutting the fruit or pulp transversely at the midpoint and placing the measuring head at the centre of each half.
- Measuring the colour of boiled plantain pulp: First, plantain fruit was washed and peeled. Second, the pulp was transferred to a pan with sufficient boiling water and cooked for varying periods of time (10 to 60 minutes). Third, after each cooking time, the plantain pulps are removed and left to cool for 5 minutes at room temperature. Fourth, the measurements were carried out at a temperature range comprised between 55°C and 60°C. The pulp was cut transversely (2cm long), then transferred to the reading tray and the chromameter head placed at the centre of the fruit, then readings were taken.

Figure 2: Workflow of colour measurements using a Chromameter

7 EXPRESSION OF RESULTS

After obtaining each parameter, the colour intensity (ΔE) was calculated using the following equations

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(\Delta L)^2 + (\Delta a)^2 + (\Delta b)^2}$$

Where ΔL , Δa , Δb represents the derivation of the individual values from their respective sample.

$$\Delta E = ((L^*_{0} - L^*)^2 + (a^*_{0} - a^*)^2 + (b^*_{0} - b^*)^2)^{1/2}$$

Where subscript "0" is the initial values of L^* , a^* and b^* at time T_0 (raw pulps).

Below is a table showing how the values read are been recorded

Table 2: Sample data recording for colour of fruits

Plantain varieties	Maturity stage	Cooking time (mins)	Pulp colour parameters			
			L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE
CARBAP K74	Unripe green (Stage 1)	T0 (raw)	77,51	1,38	27,55	0,00
		T10	68,07	-2,82	30,22	11,34
		T20	62,63	-2,57	29,43	16,03
		T30	56,46	-2,11	26,25	21,53
		T40	51,64	-0,89	29,18	26,48
		T50	53,97	0,44	26,29	23,78
		T60	51,90	-1,13	30,34	25,91

$$\Delta E = ((L^*_{0} - L^*)^2 + (a^*_{0} - a^*)^2 + (b^*_{0} - b^*)^2)^{1/2}$$

$$\Delta E_{T10} = ((77,51 - 68,07)^2 + (1,38 - (-2,82))^2 + (27,55 - (30,22))^2)^{1/2}$$

$$\Delta E = 11,34$$

8 CRITICAL POINTS OR NOTE ON THE PROCEDURE

- The sample preparation and reading must be completed within 5 minutes;
- The white calibration standard must always be clean before Minolta CR- 400 Chroma Meter head is placed on it;
- Minolta CR- 400 Chroma Meter must be calibrated against white standard before taking sample readings;
- Always clean the glass of the chromameter after reading the values;

- Reading on the peels must be taken on 3 different spots and mean value taken to represent the colour value for the fruit peel.
- The L*, a* and b* parameters of cooked pulp are taken 5 minutes after cooking, when the temperature is approximately 50-60°C, corresponding to the temperature at which cooked products are often consumed.
- The SD = $-1 \geq 0 \leq 1$ is acceptable. The lower the SD and the %CV (≤ 5) the better the stability and performance of the Chromameter.